

Hartford Medical Society

Blog posts from the HMS Historical Library 2015

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History of the Book: A Homeopathy Text

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There is no question that digitized materials are convenient and useful. Many of the books in the HMS collection are available online and this gives greater exposure and access to our materials. Every once in a while, however, a story unfolds that could only come from the book itself. Some time ago a patron visited the library interested in homeopathic medicine. One of our books* was found to contain an inscription, two letters, a newspaper clipping and a Christmas card tucked inside the front cover. The two letters give the history of how the book came to the HMS library. It was donated in 1946 by a retired Navy captain then living in a veteran's hospital. The newspaper clipping states that he had been given the book when he was a pharmacist's mate on the USS Marblehead during the Spanish American War. He was told at that time that the book had been used as a reference in treating sailors on the USS Hartford during the Civil War.

Is this hard proof that the book saw naval action aboard the Hartford? Not necessarily, but the book was published in 1858, so it's not out of the question. The captain clearly treasured it. He writes that "for 49 years . . . I have kept and guarded this old book from harm", and the card says —Hope you enjoy the Homeopathic Physician.

Technology has changed both how we do medicine and how we access information. Forward thinking is primarily a good thing, and something to be celebrated, but we can also use technology as a lens to look back and see that we are not so very different from our 19th century counterparts. Online library catalogs and digitized materials show evidence of the same concerns with health and healing and the delivery of healthcare to those injured in war that we have today. Our fear of the uncontrollable and the unknown is no less than that of 200 years ago; we're just focused on different specifics. You can reach out digitally across the centuries and find someone pretty much like yourself. But if you really want to shake hands with a sentimental seafaring man, visit the library.

*[Pulte, J H. *Homoeopathic Domestic Physician: Containing the Treatment of Diseases; Popular Explanations of Anatomy, Physiology, Hygiene and Hydrophathy,*

Remedies for the Gout

January 6, 2015

Gout! a disease known to the ancient Greeks and Egyptians and still with us today, although with far better remedies. Gout was known as “The Rich Man’s Disease” because it was associated with a diet high in red meat and lots of alcohol¹. In reality, the causes of those nasty little uric acid crystals in the joints are many and varied and certainly not the sole provenance of the rich.

Recipes for curing gout are legion, and go back as far as the records of the disease itself. The following unusual cure was among the recipes in the herbal of Thomas Betson (d. 1517)²:

For all goutis:

Take an ole and poule him and opyn him as thou wolde ete him, and salt him wel and do him in an erthyn pot, and ley a bord theron and set it into a little hoven where men set in dogh. And whan men draw forth, lok if thi oule be ynough for to make purdur, and if it be not, let it stand still to it be ynough, and then bet it to powdur and temper it with bore grese, and anoint the seke by the fire. [p. 252]

Translation:

Take an owl and pluck him and open him as thou would eat him, and salt him well and do him in an earthen pot, and lay a board thereon and set it into a little oven where men set in dough. And when men draw forth, look if the owl be enough [baked] for to make powder, and if it be not, let it stand still to it be enough and then beat it to powder and temper it with boar grease and anoint the sick by the fire.

The images on the preceding page are from a book in the collection of the Hartford Medical Society Historical Library, dated 1722³.

This volume is made unique by the handwritten documents stitched in at the front and back of the printed text. These include additional recipes for treating gout along with copies of letters, also on the same topic, including a copy of a letter written by the author of the printed text – Dr. George Cheyne.

Transcription:
 I am very glad Providence has put in my power to do you a small piece of service which I hope by the Divine Blessing now to perform. Your case is entirely hypocondriacal, from the goutish humours being confined inwardly and not spent on the joints thro the winter cold, and stoppage of the perspiration; and I will tell you a piece of natural Philosophy not very common that the Bodies of Declining Valitudinary Persons, or those afflicted with a chronical

if they remove not into a warm climate, their Blood circulates so slow, sluggishly & imperfectly, that from Midwinter to Midsummer [vide my Treatise P. 10 that of Health P. 192] they are only alive, and that till the sun has new animated, melted and rarify'd and fermented their Juices, they do not get up to Cheerfulness & Freedom of Spirits, to chirp sing & Propagate: In some this begins sooner and ends later, but in the lowest of Times are much as I have assign'd them. = For your cure, get species of Hiera Pira an ounce, a Dram of Cochineal, two Drams of Snakeweed, an ounce of Spirit of lavender, and as much Tincture of Callor. Mix all these with about 3 half pints or a little more, of Good Mountain; by a warm fire side, in a well corked bottle for six days, then strain it thro a linnen rag into a clean Bottle, and every other night take 2 or 3 or 4 Spoonfulls going to bed, so as to give you 2 or 3 motions as you can bear them, at night take a large Pill or little Button of Venice Treacle and after it a Glass of sack whey, eat light food and Drink old Port with some German Spaw, or Pyrmont waters from London, if you can get 'em = This will either cure you or give you a fit of ye Gout, we will do it effectually = As for your Friend had you consider'd my Book, you woud have seen that ye Bath waters, are ye Best of all Remedies for the Palty, with ye Reason why in a word, all ye Paralytick that are able to be brot hither, come to they Place & are generally Reliev'd, if not quite cur'd =
 I am P^r Your Servant Jos: Clayton

distemper, have a great analogy to Batts, insects, owls, and the birds that are called birds of a Season, that if they remove not into a warm climate, their blood circulates so slow, sluggishly and imperfectly, that from midwinter to midsummer [vide my treatise p. 10 that of Health P. 192] they are only alive, and that till the sun has new animated, melted and rarify'd and fermented their juices, they do not get up to cheerfulness and freedom of spirits, to chirp sing and propagate: In some this begins sooner and ends later, but in the lowest the times are much as I have assign'd them. = For your cure get species of Hiera Pira, an ounce, a dram of cochineal, two drams of snakeweed, and ounce of spirit of lavender, and as much tincture of callor [castor].

Mix all these with about 3 half pint or a little more, of good mountain [spirits]; by a warm fire side, in a well cork'd bottle for six days, then strain it thro a linen rag into a clean bottle and every other night take 2 or 3 spoonfulls going to bed, so as to give you 2 or 3 motions as you can bear them, at night take a large pill or little button of Venice Treacle and after it a glass of sack whey, eat light food and drink old port with some German spaw [spa], or Pymont [mineral] waters from London, if you can get 'em = This will either cure you or give you a fit of the gout which will do it effectually = as for your Friend, had you consider'd my Book, you woud have seen that the Bath waters are the best of all remedies for the Palsy, with the Reason why, in a word, all the Paralytics that are able to be brot hither, come to this place and are generally Reliev'd if not quite cur'd = I am Sr., Your Servant Geo: Cheyne -

Some notes on ingredients in this cure:

- **Hiera Piera:** is a variant of Hiera Picra, probably aloes and canella (*Canella winteriana* - wild cinnamon bark) powder, used as a purgative
- **Snakeweed:** probably *Bryonia alba*, also a purgative
- **Tincture of callor:** probably tincture of castor, an extract of dried, preputial follicles of the beaver

Venice Treacle: an ancient remedy and expensive mixture composed of 64 ingredients including viper flesh and opium; also called Theriac. This was used as an antidote to poison, something along the lines of the Homeopathic mantra that “like cures like”. This might account for George Cheyne’s comment: “*This will either cure you or give you a fit of the gout, which will do it effectually.*”

It is interesting to note that owls are again mentioned in connection with gout. In this case someone with a propensity to gout is likened to seasonal 'birds' such as bats, insects and owls which decline in winter unless they migrate. The cold and dark apparently stop the 'goutish humors' from exiting via perspiration thus explaining their concentration in the joints.

Happily, today an acute attack of gout can be treated with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs), colchicine or corticosteroids. No baked owls needed.

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Not Everything “Natural” is Good for You

February 17, 2015

It's not often that one comes across a word that has no definition, but here's one: **Spinevantosey**. This word appears in a little pamphlet, printed in 1827, titled “Dr. John Williams’ Last Legacy or The Useful Family Herbal”.

Here is remedy #62:

“For the spinevantosey that comes in the breast.

Take spikenard root, cumfrey root, yellow oak bark, and tobacco, boil them in water, strong, take out some of the liquor to wash the tumour, add to the rest hog’s lard or mutton tallow, beeswax and rosin, simmer it over a slow fire, stir it constantly until it is salve, apply it to the sore, physic with mandrake roots three or four times. Bleed once.”

The author of this pamphlet, Dr. John Williams, is described in an advertisement for this work as follows:

“The author of this work is a native of New-York, and now resides in Washington county, in the easterly part of the state; he has for the most part of his life been engaged in the deepest study for restoring the health and preserving the lives of his fellow creatures. For the attainment of this object he has travelled. To this end he has laboured, and for years has applied himself in the wilds of America, among the natives of the forest, where he has undergone all the horrors and deprivations incident to savage life, in order to collect and bring together that knowledge which should be instrumental in saving the lives and preserving the health of his fellow creatures.

Whilst among the Indians, the author was a particular inmate and confidant of a native Indian, who had been instructed in all the arts of civilized life, and had the advantages of a liberal education, being a regular bred physician, in the medical department of the Pennsylvania university, established at Philadelphia, at once the most flourishing and respectable institution of the kind in the United States, and hardly excelled by any in Europe. – While with this Indian, the author of this work had not only an opportunity of learning the Indian method of treating disorders, and the medical virtues of the vegetable kingdom, but likewise of gaining much literary and scientific knowledge.” 1.

Thus this recipe – a fusion of Native American herbal medicine and medicine as taught at the Pennsylvania University medical department – is the best that Dr. Williams could offer in 1827. “Spinevantosey” appears to be breast cancer.

The 'active ingredients' in this recipe are:

Spikenard root – According to Wikipedia there are several plants that may be called “spikenard”. Most common is *Nardostachys jatamansi*, native to the Himalayas, which has been used since antiquity to produce an aromatic oil. Spikenard may also refer to all plants of the genus *Aralia*; false spikenard, or wild spikenard, plant species from the *Smilacina* genus; *Lavandula stoechas*, (Nard) - another species used in antiquity to produce an aromatic oil; Ploughman's-spikenard, *Inula conyza*; Wild spikenard, *Asarum europaeum*.

Cumfrey [Comfrey] root, *Symphytum officinalis* - contains liver-toxic pyrrolizidine alkaloids.

Yellow oak bark – probably *Quercus velutina* Eastern Black Oak, the bark of which yields a yellow dye

Tobacco – genus *Nicotiana* reputed to be a cure-all in many cultures.

Mandrake root – genus *Mandragora* used historically as an analgesic but contains hallucinogenic and anticholinergic compounds.

The precise species of several of these ingredients is unknown, as are quantities, and exact preparation. There was also no understanding of the chemistry of the compounds in these botanicals and their physiological action on the body. These ingredients include a liver toxin, an addictive stimulant, and a hallucinogen.

Have we progressed? We certainly have a better understanding of breast cancer, along with sophisticated drugs and surgical procedures for treating it. On the other hand, a quick Google search on “natural remedies breast cancer” brings up over 1.5 million hits. Vitamins, oils, baking soda, special diets, mistletoe and many other botanicals are listed. Some of these are to be used in conjunction with traditional therapy. Some sites talk darkly about conspiracy; the “cash cow” of cancer treatment and a lack of incentives to cure cancer on the part of pharmaceutical companies and physicians. “Natural” treatments equal Good on these sites, and scientific remedies are Bad. These proponents not only need a cure for spinevantosey, they need a cure for fear and narrow thinking. And what remedy is there in a doctor’s bag for that?

What was the role of women in 19th and early 20th century healthcare? Much has been written about the female pioneers in nursing and medicine, but one could argue that practically all women were responsible for basic health care delivery for their immediate families. Printed texts of home remedies doubled as recipe books as in the example above, “published by a distinguished physician” (not named, 1853,) from our collection [1]. The title page of this work states: “These instructions are perfectly reliable and safe, and if followed will save hundreds of dollars in avoiding doctor’s bills.”

The thesis of Rima Apple’s 1995 paper: “Constructing Mothers: Scientific Motherhood in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries” [2] is that, over the course of the early 20th century, women were increasingly seen “as both responsible for their families and incapable of that responsibility.” According to Apple, “in the nineteenth century women were exhorted to seek out information for themselves.” As medicine became more systematic and the causes of disease were better understood, there was a growing divide between formal medical education and lay knowledge. While women as mothers were expected to be moral guides their scientific knowledge was increasingly suspect. Apple calls this “scientific motherhood” which she defines as “the insistence that women require expert scientific and medical advice to raise their children healthfully.” There were financial incentives driving this transition. Physicians certainly wanted patients, but there were also many commercial products such as infant formula and baby food, toiletries and cleaning products that were created out of the new sciences, (nutrition, hygiene,) that depended on women for their success.

Let's look at *Library of Health*, published in 1916, also in the HMS collection. [3] It is a massive tome – 1772 pages – and it falls fairly in the middle of Apple's described transition period. There are substantial sections on "Anatomy and Physiology", "The Diagnosis of Disease" and "Medical Materials, Their Properties and Uses". Here is the purpose of this work as given in the introduction:

"This knowledge is not intended to make doctors out of laymen or to encourage self-medication except in emergency. It aims to teach *prevention* rather than *cure* . . . The mother is the one who looks after the health of the family. The mother is with the children twenty-four hours in the day and feels most responsible in case of sickness. That is why the "Library" is

placed in the homes – IT IS FOR THE WIFE and FOR THE MOTHER

[original emphasis] . . .

Knowing from our experience that the medical specialists and teachers who stand at the head of their profession write in language of technical expression . . . [we] have put the technical and scientific knowledge in a plain, practical form, so that anyone can understand."

If the language is "dumbed down", the content is not; the science of the times is there.

Just as prominent in *Library of Health* is the era's morality.

Take for example these colorful plates and their equally colorful description:

“This exquisitely beautiful and artistic Anatomical Plate presents the head and face of a young man in the enjoyment of perfect health. . .

Note the prominent perceptive faculties, the high forehead, features characteristic of a large brain and a massive and unimpaired intellect. Mark the open expression of the eye! how true to nature and life-like. Observe the compressed lips, denoting firmness of character and determination of purpose. Look attentively at the bright, open, manly countenance; there are no signs of mental decrepitude, physical bodily infirmities, nervous fear, or exhaustion of brain power or life-force in the expression of the noble, ruddy and healthy face. It is, as its name implies, typical of *Perfect Health!*” [p. 35]

The moral mantle of a wife and mother was a heavy one. The following quotes all come from the *Library of Health* section on “Sexology” pages 1107-1198:

- “The marriage of unhealthy persons is liable to lead to distressing consequences. Hereditary transmission of diseases enters into the moral as well as physical order of things. This is especially true of scrofulous people, who, as a rule, are prolific. Even if the exact hereditary taint does not pass to the offspring, there is liability to a train of the common diseases which mar comfort and destroy life.” [p.1108]
- “The courage and sublimity of woman’s nature is inherent, descending through ages, thus becoming a fixed moral quantity of woman in her kind.” [p. 1109]
“Sexual emotion is absolutely necessary to conception. The impress is made at the moment. Every quality of mind of body which is dominant then will undoubtedly determine the fate of the offspring. How imperatively necessary it is, then, at that moment, to permit nothing but the most pleasant fancies to occupy the mind, namely the thought of those actions and things which are most desirable to reappear in children.” [p.1110]

How did these notions of science and morality play out as the century advanced? Home health care and the science of child rearing were increasingly relegated to ‘the experts’. Apple cites a 1938 advertisement for Libby’s baby food where a clean-cut couple is discussing their infant son’s diet:

- Father: But your mother says he’s much too young for vegetables!
- Mother: Well dear, you’d better argue that with Doctor Evans. He says babies do better if they have vegetables early in life.

In 1946, Dr. Benjamin Spock first published his phenomenally popular *The Common Sense Book of Baby and Child Care*. [4] Today, there are apparently unlimited sources of medical and child-rearing information. Perhaps a physician is needed to point the way through the morass.

It sounds quaint today, or archaic, to think of women as the keepers of moral rectitude in the family but it may not be as far-fetched as it seems. One wonders if the current violent debate over whether or not to vaccinate has some roots in this old medical/moral divide.

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Cigarette Smoking and the Medical Profession

April 27, 2015

Cigarette advertising cards: Allen & Ginter [late 19th century.]

Tobacco was in common use in the 19th century, the most common modalities for using it being cigars, snuff and hand-rolled cigarettes, rolled by the consumer. Pre-rolled cigarettes were not readily available until machines for rolling were developed in the 1880s. At this point the sale of cigarettes in packs, reinforced with pieces of cardboard, became common. Mr. James Buchanan Duke, of W. Duke & Sons in Durham had the inspired marketing idea of printing the name of the cigarette company on the card along with colorful images of popular sports figures which could be collected and traded. ¹

This idea was quick to catch on. The two cards on the previous page are from the company of Allen & Ginter. William Muldoon was a world champion in Greco-Roman wrestling. He learned how to wrestle in the Civil War camps of the North. John L. Sullivan, a boxer, was considered to be one of the best heavyweights ever. He was the link between bare knuckles and glove fighting. ²

By the turn of the 19th century, there was concern about the health effects of smoking, especially in the young:
"Juvenile smoking is spreading like an epidemic. It is impossible to estimate the injury which boys are thus doing themselves. Surely something should be done, and done promptly to put a stop to all this mischief."-R. MARTIN.
This quote is at the head of an article published in 1900. ³

The author, Dr. Breña, is concerned with small stature, low body weight (considered a problem in those days) and reduced lung capacity in boys who smoke as children or adolescents. He cites the following statistics:
"In 187 members of the Yale class of 1891 it was seen that those who were not addicted to smoking increased in weight during the scholastic period 10.4 percent, more than the habitual smoker, and 6.6 percent more than those who smoked cigarettes only at rare intervals. Furthermore, those of the first group exceeded in stature those of the second by 24 percent and those of the third group by 12 per cent. Comparative measurements of the circumference of the thorax showed an average of 26.7 and 22 percent, respectively, in favor of the nonsmoker, as also a respiratory capacity of 77.5 and 49 percent greater than that of the rest of the students."

Smoking by girls is not mentioned.

The costs and benefits of smoking continued to be debated over the next century. Clearly there were financial incentives to promoting the beneficial effects of cigarette smoking. Here is a quote from O.A. Kenyon of the Axton-Fisher Tobacco Company, and a chart, from his 1934 pamphlet *Theory and Facts of Cigarette Smoking*:

“Cigarette smoking is a phenomenon of modern life. It gives tobacco entirely new and different characteristics from those developed by pipe and cigar smoking. It has added to the joy of living.” [p. 3] ⁴

WHY DO WE SMOKE?

THE best answer to this question was obtained by Dr. Bogen of the University of Cincinnati in an extensive investigation* which he made of cigarette smoking and cigarette smokers. The reasons given for enjoyment of smoking are charted in Fig. 2. The height of the different factors represents the percentage of people who mentioned the particular characteristic as a reason for enjoying cigarette smoking.

*Journal American Medical Assoc. Vol. 95, No. 15.

FIG. 2. Six hundred people gave the above as reasons for smoking cigarettes. The total is greater than 100% because many gave more than one reason.

While physicians were increasingly aware of the risks, they found it difficult to come up with compelling evidence of harm, especially in the face of such a popular habit. The 1957 book, *Science looks at smoking: A new inquiry into the effects of smoking on your health*, is still wrestling with this question:

“It is a paradox of our times that tobacco, the most universal of acquired human appetites should become a major source of man’s anxiety. . . There may, of course, be many legitimate reasons for the desire of some persons to quit smoking. It’s expensive . . . it’s messy, often causing discoloration of the teeth and nails; it sometimes results in mildly unpleasant side reactions – wooly mouth, cigarette cough, hoarseness. . . It would be unrealistic to deny, however, that for a majority of smokers, tobacco represents considerably more than a casual “take-it-or-leave-it” item of consumption. **The key to its importance is perhaps best expressed in a recent statement of the *Journal of the American Medical Association*: “From a psychological point of view more can be said in behalf of smoking as an escape from nervous tension than against it.”** [emphasis added] . . . But many confirmed smokers now feel shaken by the suspicion, often headlined as a fact, that cigarettes cause cancer and heart disease. This book has tried to demonstrate that despite such headlines, all those who have attempted to prove the evil effects of tobacco have failed to establish a valid scientific case.” [pp. 178-9] ⁵

A recent addition to the HMS collection is documentary evidence of this attitude. . . .

This item was donated by a current faculty member at UConn Health. It belonged to her physician grandfather, John Earl Stanton, M.D. (1891-1970). The fact that no one today would dream of presenting a gift of an ashtray with a Caduceus as an ornament shows how far we have come – and how recently.

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Sticks and Stones

May 15, 2015

Nebuchadnezzar 1795/circa 1805 William Blake 1757-1827 Presented by W. Graham Robertson 1939 <http://www.tate.org.uk/art/work/N05059>

The stigma of mental illness is hard to escape. The bestial conception of people so afflicted is visually – and viscerally – represented in William Blake's haunting 1795 image of Nebuchadnezzar.

The Report on insanity and idiocy in Massachusetts by the Commission on Lunacy under resolve of the Legislature of 1854, (call # WM 28 AM4 M411r 1855 in the HMS collection,) gives the following statistics:

“... the Commission have ascertained that there were in the autumn of 1854, in the state of Massachusetts, two thousand six hundred and thirty-two lunatics, and ten hundred and eighty-seven idiots – making a total of three thousand seven hundred and nineteen of these persons who need the care and protection of their friends or of the public for their support, restoration or custody” p. 17 [1].

“Lunatic”. “Idiot”. These are not words we would use professionally today, in fact they are considered derogatory and insulting, and yet they were in common usage in the 19th century, used as above in conjunction with “care” and “protection”. The words we use evolve naturally over time, but sometimes their evolution is the result of conscious efforts by specific groups.

Can words hurt? There is certainly a groundswell of opinion that they can. “Trigger Warnings” are now requested by students on college campuses to spare those who may have upsetting events in their own lives recalled by words in required readings or audiovisuals. [2] Just this month, the World Health Organization issued guidelines for the naming of infectious diseases “with the aim to minimize unnecessary negative impact of disease names on trade, travel, tourism or animal welfare, and avoid causing offence to any cultural, social, national, regional, professional or ethnic groups.” [3]

Mental illness is an area where words seem to have particular power. In the nineteenth century, the words “idiot” and “imbecile” were used for people with developmental difficulties while “lunatic” was used for less tangible forms of mental illness. [4]

Much has been written about the term “lunatic” which was apparently used as early as the late 14th century to describe an unspecified pathological condition. While early uses of the term in Greek point to epilepsy, the link with psychiatric diseases was forged by the 4th century, and “lunatic,” indicating mental illness, was in widespread use in English in the late 16th century. [5] In the early 19th century, the pull of the moon was felt to be so strong that those in charge of mental patients intervened proactively:

“In 1833 the physician Haslam in reviewing his new assignment as director of Bethlehem Royal Hospital in London wrote ‘Indeed I have understood from such of these lunatics who have recovered that the overseer or master of the work-house himself has frequently been so much under the dominion of this planet (the moon)... that without waiting for any display of increased turbulence on the part of the patient, he bound, chained, flogged and deprived these miserable people of food, according as he discovered the moon’s age by the almanac’ “ [6]

Many practitioners who treated people with mental illness worked hard to change the language as they worked to raise the status of their specialty. “Asylums” were to be called “hospitals”; “lunatics”, with the word’s unscientific association with lunar cycles, were to be called “insane”. [4] Today’s technology allows us to scan huge swaths of digitized text to chart the rise and fall in the use of specific words over time.

Here is a graphic generated using Google’s Ngram Viewer:

One can see that the use of “lunatic” declines in the 1880s while the word “insane” was in heavy use until 1918 or so.

Of course the words used to describe mental illness are just a very small part of a larger picture. What constitutes “mental illness”? Elizabeth Packard was institutionalized for 3 years by her husband in the 1860s for questioning her Reverend husband’s theological views. When released from custody, she became an activist, writing about her experience. [7] People have often been institutionalized because they saw the world differently, or because it was politically expedient. Once inside, it is very hard to convince the authorities of one’s sanity as anyone who has read Ken Kesey’s *One Flew Over the Cuckoo’s Nest* can attest. Between 1980 and 1990 a publication titled *Phoenix Rising* was published in Toronto, written by former mental institution patients to raise awareness around the stigma of mental illness and institutionalization. [8]

As the WHO guidelines and all the current talk about trigger warnings suggest, the words we use are still weighed and considered today.

Perhaps this is even more of a concern in an era when information travels so widely and quickly. Only so much can be driven intentionally, however. One wonders what future Ngrams will look like when texts using expressions like “crazy busy!” and “that idea is totally insane!” are included.

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The Brilliance-Radiance Balance

What drives people to seek out new knowledge? Some may do it for prestige, or with a specific goal in mind. Others seem to be motivated by some internal driver.

Tucked away on a shelf in the HMS library is a biography of Marie Skłodowska Curie (7 November 1867 – 4 July 1934.) (Curie & Sheean, 1937) The pages are yellow and the book jacket is poorly mended with adhesive tape, but Madame Curie stares out from the cover with a piercing and uncompromising gaze.

The book was written by the younger of her two daughters and is inscribed by the author. It was clearly purchased at a promotional talk given by Eve Curie. A postcard and newspaper clipping announcing the talk are inserted into the book.

By all accounts, Marie Skłodowska was a brilliant student who taught herself to read at age 4, had a near-photographic memory and was fluent in 5 languages. She was the youngest of 5 children, born into an intellectual Polish family at a time when Poland did not exist. The Warsaw she grew up in was under Russian rule. By the age of 10 she had lost her eldest sister to typhus, and her mother to tuberculosis. She was well educated, for a woman of those days, and continued to study on her own when she was working as a governess in her late teens and early twenties.

Mme. Curie's subsequent accomplishments, her discovery of Polonium and Radium, her efforts during World War I bringing mobile x-ray units to the battlefield and her 2 Nobel Prizes are well documented but one has the impression that she would have conducted her life the same way with no recognition. She drove herself without stinting, and died in 1934 of aplastic anemia, the result of radiation poisoning. Descriptions of her life usually talk about the sacrifices she made in the same breath as her greatness.

A recent article in the *New York Times Magazine*, (Greenwood, 2014) paints a more complex portrait of Curie. The author is the great great niece of Marguerite Perey, who worked in the Curie's Radium Institute for 30 years. Perey was the daughter of a local flour mill owner who attended the local vocational college for chemistry technicians. Top in her class, she was hired at age 19 to work as Mme Curie's assistant. Perey discovered the element Francium, and eventually received her PhD from the Sorbonne in 1946. She died of bone cancer in 1975.

The article describes other, more sudden deaths among the staff at the Institute, along with gruesome injuries and disabilities.

The landmark Radium Girls case was settled in June 1928, so the hazards of radiation exposure were clearly known. Why, then, was the Radium Institute not more careful to limit exposure? Curie went from Brilliant to – literally – Radiant. According to Wikipedia, her papers are so radioactive that they are stored in lead lined containers and researchers must wear protective gear to use them. Greenwood's theory is that bravado played a part. She gives the example of staff physicist Cecile DeWill-Morette quoting Mme. Curie's daughter Irène Joliot-Curie saying "anyone who worried about radiation hazards was not a dedicated scientist." Greenwood writes: "You almost get the impression that in the Curie lab, dedication to science was demonstrated by a willingness to poison yourself."

As of 2014, the Nobel Prize had been awarded to 887 people, 47 of whom were women, (5%). Certainly Curie deserves her stellar reputation. She has been held up as an example to young women the world over. One wishes however, that there were more exemplary women given as examples.

The comic XKCD, drawn by Randall Munroe makes this point nicely, (see his comic #896 on the next page). Of special note is "Zombie Curie's" advice: "You don't become great by trying to become great. You become great by wanting to do something, and then doing it so hard that you become great in the process."

Curie, E., & Sheean, V. (1937). *Madame Curie: a biography* ([1st ed.]. Garden City, N.Y.: Doubleday Doran & Co.

Greenwood, V. (2014, December 3, 2014). My Great-Great-Aunt Discovered Francium. And it Killed Her. *New York Times Magazine*.

XKCD <https://xkcd.com/896/>

Poetry of the American Civil War

July 13, 2015

The HMS library holds perhaps the only complete set of issues of the *Knight Hospital Record*.

This newsletter was published by the Knight Hospital of New Haven, from October 1864 to July 1865. Overwhelming numbers of war casualties necessitated a rapid governmental response and led to the creation of a military hospital hierarchy. Casualties from the battlefields were triaged on site and then transported by wagon to local hospitals. If soldiers survived this far, they were transported by boat or train to hospitals such as the Knight Hospital where they would recuperate and either be discharged home or sent back to the front. This weekly 4-page newsletter printed news of the war, descriptions of soldiers' experiences, small colorful news items, advertising, and poetry. Many of the Poems of the *Knight Hospital Record* have recently been transcribed by Dr. Ira Spar and are now available online at <<http://library.uchc.edu/hms/KnightHospPoems-ToC.html>>

Dr. Spar is the author of "New Haven's Civil War Hospital : a history of Knight U.S. General Hospital, 1862-1865" (Spar, 2014). The categories into which he has grouped the poems say a lot about the poems themselves. In the Soldier's Life and Battlefield Death categories the topics are loneliness and homesickness, loss and dying, grief but also pride.

This is from "Death of the Soldier":

Where the sweet magnolia blossoms
"Neath a sunny southern sky,
Where the breezes softly murmur,
He had fallen there to die.
But a comrade watched beside him,
Through that long and weary day,
Listening to the words he uttered
For the loved ones far away.

This, from "The Soldier":

For gold the merchant plows the main,
The farmer plow's the manor;
But glory is the soldier's prize;
The soldier's wealth is honor;
The brave poor soldier ne'er despise,
Nor count him as a stranger;
Remember he's his country's stay
In day and hour of danger.

In the Patriotism and Politics categories poems call out the Rebel traitors and describe battles. This is from "Sherman's in Savannah":

Glory be to God on High!
Shout the loud Hosanna!
Treason's wilderness is past,
Canaan's shore is won at last,
Peal a nation's trumpet blast;--
Sherman's in Savannah!

Poems in the Prisoners of War category are gruesome. This comes from "Prison Horrors":

No shelter know the sufferers; bolder ones
Daring to seek it, scorched by Georgian suns,
Drop on the dead-line 'neath the warders' guns.

But some are quite funny. This example comes from "A Cold in the Head," filed under 'Medical':

To spend one's time 'twixt handkerchief
And stuff, is far from fun;
They say "time" flies; 'tis also true
That noses often "run."

Quite a few are devoted to romance. This is from “I’m not Particular”:

Don’t think that I’m particular,
If I should humbly state.
The sort of ladies that I love,
And ditto, ditto ha----;
For, believe me, dearest reader,
I am not hard to please,
But—really—yes, I love the ones
That you can kiss and sq----,
Oh, yes, indeed, I am quite fond
Of those who kiss and sq----.

In the Economics category we have “Petroleum!”:

“Sink not that well,” his conscience said;
“Too big a strike may strike you dead.”
Up goes the derrick, down goes the bore,
Up comes the sand-pump, what’s flowing o’er
Petroleum!

In the introduction to her recent book, “To Fight Aloud is Very Brave: American Poetry and the Civil War”, Faith Barrett says:

. . . the versatility of poetic voice – prompted a remarkable outpouring of poetry by men and women from all walks of life during the American Civil War. The war called on Americans to make decisions about their familial, regional, and national allegiances; this demand that each individual define his or her own position in relation to the construct of the nation coincided with rising rates of literacy and with pedagogical methods and print media that promoted the cultural centrality of poetry.

The poetry of the nineteenth century has not been treated kindly by twentieth and twenty-first century critics.

“Writing in the aftermath of two world wars, mid-twentieth-century critics celebrated twentieth-century modernist poets for their commitment to an aesthetic of fragmentation, irony, and indeterminacy. Turning back to the nineteenth century, these same scholars tended to admire mainly Whitman and Dickinson, anointing them as forebears of modernism . . .” (Barrett, 2012)

Even as late as 2011 *The Atlantic Monthly* ran a piece titled: Herman Melville’s Mediocre Civil War Poetry . This dismissive view of American Civil War era poetry is currently being reexamined by literary scholars. In “Melville and the Worlds of Civil War Poetry” Elizabeth Rencker writes:

“This familiar story of Melville’s allegedly bad poetry does not engage any poems; it simply reprints the negative 1867 review of *Battle-Pieces and Aspects of the War* by William Dean Howells . . .” (Renker, 2014)

And here is Vanessa Steinroetter in her 2013 article “Reading the List”: Casualty Lists and Civil War Poetry:

“. . . these [Civil War] poems were relegated to obscurity by twentieth-century literary historians of the Civil War, who privileged the atypical proto-modernist, and experimental in poetry through lyric readings. . . Rather, it is precisely through their lack of individuality that the speakers function as representative voices of collective experiences . . . Far from offering only melodrama, jingoism, or religious didacticism, they draw attention to the contrast between public reading and private grief . . .” (Steinroetter, 2013).

Those who would like to learn more about the poetry of the American Civil War could start with this site from the Library of Congress: “To Light Us to Freedom and Glory Again”: The Role of Civil War Poetry.

Poetry has always functioned in some capacity as therapy and in recent times this aspect has received more formal attention. The National Association for Poetry Therapy has been in existence for about 30 years and their peer-reviewed journal, *The Journal of Poetry Therapy*, has been published quarterly since 1987. In the abstract of her 2010 article “Recon Mission: Familiarizing Veterans with Their Changed Emotional Landscape through Poetry Therapy”, Anjana Deshpande writes:

“Trauma needs containment and recognition in order to be handled, and this project enabled the soldier to do both through the use of writing and poetry” (Deshpande, 2010)

Whatever trauma Walt Whitman suffered as a nurse during the American Civil War he subsumed in his poetry. Here is his poem “The Wound-Dresser”

1.
An old man bending I come among new faces,
Years looking backward resuming in answer to children,
Come tell us old man, as from young men and maidens
that love me,
(Arous’d and angry, I’d thought to beat the alarum, and
urge relentless war,
But soon my fingers fail’d me, my face droop’d and I
resign’d myself,
To sit by the wounded and soothe them, or silently watch
the dead;)

Years hence of these scenes, of these furious passions, these chances,
Of unsurpass'd heroes, (was one side so brave? the other was equally brave;) Now be witness again, paint the mightiest armies of earth, Of those armies so rapid so wondrous what saw you to tell us? What stays with you latest and deepest? of curious panics, Of hard-fought engagements or sieges tremendous what deepest remains?

2.
O maidens and young men I love and that love me,
What you ask of my days those the strangest and sudden your talking recalls,
Soldier alert I arrive after a long march cover'd with sweat and dust,
In the nick of time I come, plunge in the fight, loudly shout in the rush of successful charge,
Enter the captur'd works—yet lo, like a swift running river they fade,
Pass and are gone they fade—I dwell not on soldiers' perils or soldiers' joys,
(Both I remember well—many of the hardships, few the joys, yet I was content.)

But in silence, in dreams' projections,
While the world of gain and appearance and mirth goes on,
So soon what is over forgotten, and waves wash the imprints off the sand,
With hinged knees returning I enter the doors, (while for you up there,
Whoever you are, follow without noise and be of strong heart.)

Bearing the bandages, water and sponge,
Straight and swift to my wounded I go,
Where they lie on the ground after the battle brought in,
Where their priceless blood reddens the grass, the ground,
Or to the rows of the hospital tent, or under the roof'd
hospital,
To the long rows of cots up and down each side I return,
To each and all one after another I draw near, not one do I
miss,
An attendant follows holding a tray, he carries a refuse pail,
Soon to be fill'd with clotted rags and blood, emptied, and
fill'd again.

I onward go, I stop,
With hinged knees and steady hand to dress wounds,
I am firm with each, the pangs are sharp yet unavoidable,
One turns to me his appealing eyes—poor boy! I never
knew you,
Yet I think I could not refuse this moment to die for you,
if that would save you.

3.

On, on I go, (open doors of time! open hospital doors!)
The crush'd head I dress, (poor crazed hand tear not the
bandage away,)
The neck of the cavalry-man with the bullet through and
through I examine,
Hard the breathing rattles, quite glazed already the eye, yet
life struggles hard,
(Come sweet death! be persuaded O beautiful death!
In mercy come quickly.)

From the stump of the arm, the amputated hand,
I undo the clotted lint, remove the slough, wash off the matter and blood,
Back on his pillow the soldier bends with curv'd neck and side falling head,
His eyes are closed, his face is pale, he dares not look on the bloody stump,
And has not yet look'd on it.

I dress a wound in the side, deep, deep,
But a day or two more, for see the frame all wasted and sinking,
And the yellow-blue countenance see.

I dress the perforated shoulder, the foot with the bullet-wound,
Cleanse the one with a gnawing and putrid gangrene, so sickening, so offensive,
While the attendant stands behind aside me holding the tray and pail.

I am faithful, I do not give out,
The fractur'd thigh, the knee, the wound in the abdomen,
These and more I dress with impassive hand, (yet deep in my breast a fire, a burning flame.)

4.
Thus in silence in dreams' projections,
Returning, resuming, I thread my way through the hospitals,
The hurt and wounded I pacify with soothing hand,
I sit by the restless all the dark night, some are so young,
Some suffer so much, I recall the experience sweet and sad,
(Many a soldier's loving arms about this neck have cross'd and rested,
Many a soldier's kiss dwells on these bearded lips.)

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Alchemy - The Science of Immortality

August 3 2015

Search on Google for “metal-planet affinities” and you will come up with a chart linking 7 heavenly bodies, (5 planets, the moon and the sun,) each with a different metal: the Moon with silver, Mars with iron, the Sun with gold and so on. These ancient pairings were a core concept in alchemy.

Alchemical furnace – drawing from Bulkeley manuscript #18,
HMS Historical Library

Alchemy is often seen as a mercenary endeavor, an attempt to turn base metal into gold, but 16th and 17th century alchemists saw the practice differently.

For one thing, gold was not the only objective; way before Harry Potter people were searching for the philosophers' stone.

The creation of such a stone . . . “signaled assurance of Christ’s promised return, while its use would prepare the godly

elect for their place in Christ’s thousand-year reign on earth that was to follow Judgment Day.” (Bilak, 2013)

Alchemy was no fringe science in those days but was part of chemistry, medicine and, clearly, theology as well. In fact there were no firm boundaries between any scholarly disciplines, although there were ideological camps. Galen, whose ideas about anatomy and disease had governed medicine for over 1600 years, was also trained as a philosopher.

When Paracelsus (Philippus Aureolus Theophrastus Bombastus von Hohenheim, 1493-1541) came along in the early 16th century, he argued passionately for science based on empirical observation. He believed that disease was caused by external agents, not an imbalance in the humors as the Galenists would have it. This led to his use of chemicals, particularly metals in his therapy. People in the Renaissance thought big. The microcosm reflected the macrocosm; man reflected the universe, was one with the universe. And as the universe was allied with certain metals, so metals could cure disease. (Satterstrom, 2004)

The HMS Historical Library has its own resident alchemist: Gershom Bulkeley (1635-1713). Gershom Bulkeley was born in Concord, MA and educated at Harvard, class of 1655. He moved to Connecticut in the 1660s where he served as physician and cleric, first in New London and then in Hartford and Wethersfield.

The *Boston News Letter* for December 28, 1713 published the memorial opinion that . . . "he was Eminent for his great Parts, both Natural and Acquired, being Universally acknowledged besides his good Religion and Vertue to be a Person of Great Penetration, and a sound Judgment, as well in Divinity as Politicks and Physick; having served his Country many years successively as Minister, a Judge and a Physician with great Honour to himself and advantage to others." (Steiner, 1904)

The HMS library has Bulkeley's scientific manuscripts. These are handwritten in dense script, often in other languages, and sometimes in a special code. They are a mixture of scientific/alchemical experiments, poetry, copies of extant texts, accounts and other writings. (Satterstrom, 2004) Several of these manuscripts have been digitized and uploaded to the Internet Archive.

Was alchemy just primitive chemistry, influenced by religious teachings? One could see it that way. Or, one can view it as basic scientific research framed in the paradigm of the day. Our time has its own paradigms, which, unlike the fluid disciplines of yore, are often rigid and not tolerant of viewpoints beyond a discipline's pale. We are in thrall to the virtual world, which can be just as intangible as Galen's philosophy of medicine.

The current Maker Culture is an attempt to get back to the physicality of the real world, and the Making and Knowing project < <http://www.makingandknowing.org/> > at Columbia takes this full circle. Students involved with this project are working with a 16th century French manuscript containing recipes written down by an unknown artisan.

It contains instructions for . . . “pigment-making, metal-coloring, counterfeit gem production, life-casting in metal, cannon-casting, tree-grafting, land-surveying, a practice of taxidermy to manufacture monstrous composite animals (kittens and bats), making paper mâché masks, and much more.”

The students follow the, often vague or cryptic, instructions in an attempt to reproduce the described result. Along the way they realize the necessity of clear instruction as well as the benefit of trial and error. They are becoming scholars, learning to learn from failure, to observe and experiment. For some of them, their writings will live on when they themselves are gone; additional intellectual pods launched at the future. This project was recently featured in a radio story on WHYY (May 7, 2015): “The power of failure, and other lessons from a 400-year-old 'book of secrets'”

We may think that we have come a long way from alchemy – metals and stones associated with health and eternal life – but a recent piece by Oliver Sacks in the *New York Times* would have us think again. In meditating on his own terminal illness he writes:

“Times of stress throughout my life have led me to turn, or return, to the physical sciences, a world where there is no life, but also no death.

And now, at this juncture, when death is no longer an abstract concept, but a presence— an all-too-close, not-to-be-denied presence — I am again surrounding myself, as I did when I was a boy, with metals and minerals, little emblems of eternity.” (Sacks)

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Diet - A Crust Eaten in Peace

September 11, 2015

There is much to be said for moderation in all things. In our society today there appears to be an inverse correlation between the amount of discussion about diet and the health of our nation.

Type “diet” into the Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) database, used to index articles in PubMed, and you will find at least 10 different diets ranging from Diet, Vegetarian, added in 1963, to Diet, Paleolithic, added in 2015. There are diets restricted in sodium, in fats, in proteins, and in carbohydrates. There are gluten free diets and high-fat diets listed as MeSH terms too.

In 1880, this was the entry under “corpulence” in Holland’s *Diet for the Sick* [1]:

“Corpulence. This is susceptible of decided reduction by abstinence from fatty, saccharine, and starchy substances when joined to a course of active exercise. If the excess of flesh is a source of inconvenience the following regimen, based on that of Mr. Banting, may bring it within bounds.

- For breakfast, lean meat, except pork or veal; tea or coffee without milk or sugar; a Graham cracker or bit of toast without butter:
 - before dinner [the main, midday meal] exercise to the point of free perspiration: at dinner fish or fowl or meat, excepting pork or veal; any vegetable excepting the starchy roots; a Graham cracker, claret or dry sherry wine:
 - before tea, active exercise and a good sweat: for tea, cooked fruit and toast, or a couple of Graham crackers without butter; tea or coffee without sugar or milk.
- Exercise before bedtime. . .

When [corpulence] is inherited, and not associated with ill health, the above dietary if persisted in may give great distress. As soon as this appears it must be discontinued,

and *the unwelcome but wholesome truth should be told, namely, that a plain and regular fare, with abundant exercise, will do all that is needed for health, of which the corpulence may be a necessary condition.* Accumulations of fat are not generally a sign of disease, but rather of a reserve of energy and substance, ready for the hour of need” [pp. 61-63, emphasis added.]

*Scale—graduated to Hours and Minutes
showing Healthy Digestion in ordinary (after Beaumont.)*

<i>Vegetable Food.</i>		<i>Animal Food & Fish.</i>
	6 hours	
	45	
	30	<i>Tendon boiled</i>
	15	<i>Suet Beef</i>
	5 hours	<i>Veal Friced</i>
	45	<i>Suet Mutton { Pork fat & lean</i>
<i>Cabbage boiled</i>	30	<i>{ Duck roasted { Veal broiled</i>
	15	<i>Fowls Domestic boiled</i>
<i>Vegetable Soup & Bread</i>	4 hours	<i>{ Salmon boiled, Beef fried { Egg hard boiled, Fried { Butter-Melting, Cheese</i>
<i>Sweetish or Green Corn & Beans</i>	45	<i>Mutton Soup Oyster Soup</i>
<i>Beets boiled</i>	30	<i>Sausage Fresh fried Flourider</i>
<i>Orange Carrot boiled</i>	15	<i>Put Fish</i>
<i>Fresh Wheat Bread</i>	3 hours	<i>Oysters Fresh roasted Pork recently salted Pork Steak Eggs soft boiled, Sea Bass broiled Roasted Fresh Beef Beef Steak, Pork Chicken Fricassed Salt Beef Oysters raw</i>
<i>Turnips boiled</i>	45	
<i>Brown Soup Apple Dumpling</i>	30	<i>Sucking Pig, Lamb, broiled Turkies well roasted, Jellies</i>
<i>Corn Cake baked</i>	15	<i>Milk, raw Eggs Fresh</i>
<i>Custard baked</i>	2 hours	<i>Beef Liver broiled</i>
<i>Beans boiled Cake Sponge</i>	45	<i>Brains Animal boiled</i>
<i>Parsnips Irish Potatoes roasted</i>	30	<i>Venison Steak broiled</i>
<i>Cabbage & Vinegar, raw, baked.</i>	15	<i>Eggs whipped raw.</i>
<i>Tapioca, boiled Barley</i>	1 hour	<i>Pigs Feet, Soused Tripe</i>
<i>Sago</i>		
<i>Barley Soup, Apples sweet raw</i>		
<i>Boiled Rice.</i>		

*HOURS
and
Minutes*

Almost 200 years ago (in 1822), William Beaumont, an Army surgeon stationed in Michigan, treated a fur trader named Alexis St. Martin for a stomach wound caused by a musket which had discharged at close range.

Against all odds, the patient survived, but he was left with an opening into his stomach. This

opening was covered by a flap of skin which could be moved aside. Prompted by scientific curiosity and facilitated by the gratitude of his patient, Beaumont spent several years experimenting on St. Martin. He inserted various types of food and recorded their condition upon withdrawal at various intervals. He collected gastric secretions and studied them in vitro. Eventually St. Martin had had enough and went back to Canada.

Beaumont published his observations in 1833 under the title of “Experiments and observations on the gastric juice, and the physiology of digestion” [3] The Hartford Medical Society Historical Library has two copies of this text.

The library also has several texts on special diets for those who are ill or convalescing. This “antiphlogistic diet” [from the Greek *phlogistos*: of or relating to inflammations and fevers,] is from Neal (1861) [2] :

DIET
FOR
THE SICK AND CONVALESCENT.

ANTIPHLOGISTIC DIET.

FIRST CLASS, and lowest in the scale, are vegetable substances devoid of irritating properties, and consisting of gum, starch, and sugar, in the form of liquids.

GUM WATER, (*Gum Acacia*.)

Is best prepared by dissolving an ounce of Gum Arabic in a pint of boiling water, and allowing it to stand till cool.

It is nutritious, and adapted to the highest state of gastric irritation.

INFUSION OF SLIPPERY ELM. (*Ulmus*.)

Take of the bark, sliced and bruised, one ounce; boiling water, one pint. Macerate in a covered vessel for two hours, and strain.

Clearly smooth, easy to swallow substances were dietary choices even back then. Jell-o was developed in the form we know it today back in 1897.

There is nothing extreme about diets in the 19th century, they consisted of simple, basic foods.

Today, chicken soup is mentioned as a remedy for illness, but usually with a wink. However, look up “chicken soup” in PubMed, and you will find an entry from 2003 titled “Chicken soup cure may not be a myth” [4].

You will also find very esoteric articles such as “Measurement of the radical scavenging activity of chicken jelly soup, a part of the medicated diet, 'Yakuzen', made from gelatin gel food 'Nikogori', using chemiluminescence and electron spin resonance methods” [5]. It’s nice to see that chicken soup still gets a little respect.

Diets were nothing fancy even in the first part of the 20th century. St. Mary’s Hospital, associated with the Mayo Clinic, published a diet manual in 1935 in which are listed four types of diet: liquid, soft, light, and full house.

FOREWORD

To Second Edition

The Diet Manual is simply a compilation of diet procedures employed in the treatment of disease by the Medical Staff of Saint Mary's Hospital and the Mayo Clinic.

The needs of the typical patient form the basis of the plans presented; individual differences and responses will indicate the necessary modifications. Diet outlines and menu suggestions are intended as general guides, not as absolute rules.

For valuable advice and generous assistance by members of the Medical Staff and of the Department of Nutrition, the compiler hereby makes grateful acknowledgment.

—S. M. V.

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DIET MANUAL, ST. MARY'S HOSPITAL

STANDARD HOUSE DIETS

The standard house diets are: the liquid, the soft, the light, and the full house diet.

1. The liquid diet consists of liquid foods and beverages. Feedings are given every two hours from 8 a. m. to 8 p. m.
2. The soft diet includes more substantial food and more calories.
3. The light diet is the intermediary step from semi-solid to the full diet including easily digested foods low in cellulose, adequate protein, calories, minerals and vitamins.
4. The full house diet provides all the essential nutrients in easily digestible form.

LIQUID HOUSE DIET

Approximate food value: Pro., 50 grams; Cal., 1500

DIET OUTLINE		SAMPLE MENU	
<i>Breakfast</i>		<i>Breakfast</i>	
8 a. m.	Gruel with milk 200 c. c.	8 a. m.	Strained oatmeal gruel
	Fruit juice 100 c. c.		Orange juice
	Beverage as desired		Coffee
10 a. m.	Eggnog 200 c. c.	10 a. m.	Eggnog
<i>Dinner</i>		<i>Dinner</i>	
12 m.	Cream soup 150 c. c.	12 m.	Cream tomato soup
	Jello 100 c. c.		Jello
	Milk 200 c. c.		Milk
	Beverage as desired		Coffee or tea
2 p. m.	Milk or buttermilk 200 c. c.	2 p. m.	Milk
4 p. m.	Fruit juice 200 c. c.	4 p. m.	Grape juice
<i>Supper</i>		<i>Supper</i>	
6 p. m.	Fruit juice 200 c. c.	6 p. m.	Grapefruit juice
	Junket 100 c. c.		Junket
	Milk 200 c. c.		Milk
	Beverage as desired		Coffee or tea
8 p. m.	Milk 200 c. c.	8 p. m.	Milk

The 20th century saw huge advances in clinical and laboratory science, however. This meant that many businesses could – and did – promote the science behind their products. Food production was no exception.

Here is a page from a 1935 pamphlet produced by the

United Fruit Company titled: “Dietary uses of the banana in health and disease” [6] - also in the HMS collection:

The United Fruit Company was also responsible for the “Chiquita Banana” song:

< <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RFDOI24RRAE> >

Text beneath this YouTube video says . . . “Produced by the United Fruit Company in the 40's, this commercial appeared only in movie theaters, and for over 50 years kept us humming its catchy tune. The voice of Chiquita belongs to Monica Lewis . . .”

Food is one of the pleasures of life and one of the 3 great topics of conversation – the other two being family and philosophy (or perhaps the weather). One of the luxuries of health is the ability to eat whatever one wants. As Mark Twain supposedly said: “Part of the secret of a success in life is to eat what you like and let the food fight it out inside.” Furthermore, a voluntarily restricted diet affects one’s ability to eat with friends and family, to travel and experience new cultures. For all the science of nutrition and digestion we seem no closer to a clear picture of diet and health. This is one area where the past looks like it might have had an advantage over the present. That was a time where people were generally happy simply to have enough to eat; a time where a host didn’t have to ask “Do you have any dietary restrictions?” but only to say “Bon Appétit.”

"A crust eaten in peace is better than a banquet partaken in anxiety." - Aesop

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Feeling a Little Blue

October 16, 2015

One of the best examples of the value of printed books - as opposed to virtual ones - is a book published in 1876 by General A.J. Pleasonton titled: "The influence of the blue ray of the sunlight and of the blue color of the sky: in developing animal and vegetable life; in arresting disease and in restoring health in acute and chronic disorders to human and domestic animals" (Pleasonton, 1876). The author anticipated Marshall McLuhan by almost 90 years for his medium IS his message. The book is printed in blue ink, a subtlety lost in online versions.

Color therapy has been around for a very long time and currently hovers on the border of respectability. Websites with names like "Deep Trance Now", "Colour Therapy Healing", "Vibrational Energy Medicine" and "Holistic Online" tout supposedly scientific findings about the benefits of chromotherapy. There is, however, a body of literature from peer-reviewed sources.

Green has been a traditional color for hospitals and surgical suites since the early 20th century. In 1914 San Francisco surgeon Harry Sherman chose green – the chromatic opposite of bloody red – to help him see better on the operating table.

From that time through at least the 1970s pale green was a standard color in hospitals. “It calmed patients and workers and invited inward repose.” (Pantalony, 2009). Bright green light has been considered as a treatment for depression in older patients although its utility was not borne out (Loving, Kripke, Knickerbocker, & Grandner, 2005).

Two studies from 35 years ago looked at behavioral and physiological responses to the colors pink and blue, the premise being that pink is a calming color, while blue is strengthening (Pelligrini & Schauss, 1980; Schauss, 1979). Schauss reports that in 1979:

“Two commanding officers at the U.S. Naval Correctional Center in Seattle, Washington . . . ordered that a holding cell used for initial confinement of new inmates be painted completely pink, except for the floor. . . After 223 days of continuous use as a temporary holding facility for new confinees, the results have been impressive . . . A memorandum to the Bureau of Naval Personnel, Law Enforcement and Corrections Division, Washington, D.C, written 156 days after use of the pink holding cell stated: Since initiation of this procedure on March 1, 1979, there have been no incidents of erratic or hostile behavior during the initial phase of confinement. The memorandum went on to state that the new confinees only required a maximum of 15 minutes or exposure to ensure that the potential for aggressive behavior had been reduced. The effect continues for fully thirty minutes after release from the cell!”

The 1980 study measured maximum squeeze scores from a Lafayette Dynamometer when subjects were viewing 1.5 ft. X 2 ft. pink or blue cardboard plates. Slightly reduced squeeze scores were observed – in both men and women – when viewing the pink plate. It is for the reader to judge whether or not these studies were well designed, but one can't help but detect a whiff of sexism in their color choices.

Of all the colors it seems to be blue that gets the most attention; blue, the color of the sky, of Mary's robe, the color of royal's blue blood veins, the color of truth. There appears to be a connection between blue pigment photoreceptor cells in mammals and the setting of their circadian rhythms (Miyamoto & Sancar, 1998). Studies report reduced manic behavior and mood stabilization in patients with bipolar disorder who wear glasses with lenses that block blue light (Henriksen et al., 2014; Phelps, 2008). Blue light has been effective in treating acne (Ashkenazi, Malik, Harth, & Nitzan, 2003) and more generally in wound healing due to its antibacterial properties (Adamskaya et al., 2011; Ankri, Lubart, & Taitelbaum, 2010; Dai et al., 2012; Ganz et al., 2005; Kharkwal, Sharma, Huang, Dai, & Hamblin, 2011). Blue light has been used therapeutically for infant jaundice (McDonagh, Palma, & Lightner, 1980) some cancers (Chen, 2008; Itkin & Gilcrest, 2004) and seasonal affective disorder (Glickman, Byrne, Pineda, Hauck, & Brainard, 2006; Strong et al., 2009; Vandewalle et al., 2010).

One must weigh the evidence. A theory that blue light on train station platforms would reduce night suicides in Japan does not appear to be borne out by the evidence (Ichikawa, Inada, & Kumeji, 2014). Others have urged caution when evaluating color therapy studies (O'Connor, 2011).

However, this is the declining part of the year when the days shorten and leaves turn colors of their own before shuffling away. Surely we cannot be faulted for holding out hope for color therapy. An article published this year in the journal *Technology and Health Care* confirms that we are not alone. Its title is: "Development of multi-colored LED system for therapeutic application" (Kim et al., 2015).

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